

OPTIMIZING DURUM WHEAT YIELD UNDER SHORT-TERM DRY SPELLS THROUGH VARIETY SELECTION AND IRRIGATION MANAGEMENT

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ABSTRACT. Wheat production in Tunisia, particularly of durum wheat (*Triticum durum* Desf.), is increasingly threatened by climatic instability, including recurrent droughts and erratic rainfall patterns. In this context, optimizing yield through integrated varietal selection and irrigation management is critical. This study was conducted to assess the combined effects of variety and irrigation regime on key yield components of durum wheat under sub-humid Mediterranean conditions in northern Tunisia. A factorial field experiment was conducted at the CRRGC (Oued Béja), using two contrasting cultivars, ‘Karim’ (traditional) and ‘Maali’ (improved) under three irrigation regimes: full irrigation, deficit irrigation, and rainfed. Results revealed significant effects of variety, irrigation, and their interaction on biological yield, grain yield, and harvest index (HI). ‘Maali’ exhibited superior reproductive traits, higher spike density, greater grain yield stability, and consistently higher HI under reduced irrigation and rainfed conditions, affirming its suitability for climate-resilient systems. Conversely, ‘Karim’ demonstrated higher biomass under full irrigation but experienced sharp yield declines under water stress, suggesting a dependence on high-input conditions. Moderate deficit irrigation enhanced biomass accumulation and spike number, while maintaining acceptable grain yield, confirming the potential of precision water management in resource-limited environments. Soil analyses showed neutral pH and low salinity, ensuring that treatment effects were not confounded by edaphic factors. The findings emphasize the importance of genotype selection and strategic irrigation in enhancing productivity and resource-use efficiency. These insights contribute to sustainable cereal production under climate change scenarios and support adaptive agricultural planning in the North African region.

Keywords: Irrigation, climate variability, Yield, Durum Wheat, food security

INTRODUCTION

Food security is crucial for broader sustainable development [1]. Food security is attained when people can physically, socially, and economically have access to enough safe and nourishing food that fits their tastes and keeps them healthy [2]. Among the world’s staple crops, wheat stands out as a major calorie source for billions. In the Middle East and North Africa, wheat is more than a central component of human diets; it also implies social and economic stability. Tunisia illustrates this dependence: durum wheat (*Triticum durum* Desf.) occupies over half the country’s rainfed cereal land and supplies roughly 70 percent of its wheat harvest [3]. Yet production output never meets total demand, creating a lasting grain import shortfall. Historically, Tunisia was considered the “granary of Rome,” thanks to its strong cereal-producing potential [4].

However, nowadays, the wheat production system faces multifaceted constraints, including recurrent droughts, erratic rainfall, production costs, and degradation of natural resources [5,6].

Climate projections suggest that by 2050, Tunisia and all the North African region will face an increase of about 2.1 °C in average temperature and a 20% reduction in annual precipitation [6]. The impact of such changes threatens rainfed farming systems and the food security of smallholder communities that are particularly vulnerable to climate variability. In addition, widespread soil degradation—particularly water erosion in northern Tunisia—further compromises land productivity and reduces the resilience of cereal-based systems [7]. From a physiological perspective, wheat is highly sensitive to water stress, with effects depending on both the timing and intensity of drought.

At early-season, water stress may restrict tillering speed and vegetative growth. However, water deficits during reproductive stages lead to more severe damage to biomass partitioning and grain filling [5]. Moreover, drought conditions increase the accumulation of reactive oxygen species (ROS), triggering oxidative stress and cellular damage. *In response, the plant activates its enzymatic defenses* such as superoxide dismutase (SOD), catalase (CAT), and peroxidases (POD) [7]. Globally, half of wheat-growing areas *are already subject to recurrent drought* [8]. Consequently, the development of production systems that enhance resilience and yield stability under stress is increasingly critical.

In this situation, increasing the productivity of durum wheat will necessitate integrated solutions that incorporate adaptive water-use techniques with genetically resilient cultivars. New cultivars like "Maali," which were created to better face heat and drought, may perform better under stress. At the same time, deficit irrigation has become a practical way to save water while maintaining crop yields [9]. Testing variety-specific responses under various irrigation scenarios is essential because the efficacy of these innovations depends on how well they work together. Even though breeding and irrigation techniques have advanced significantly, there is still a significant knowledge gap regarding how wheat genotypes interact with irrigation regimes in practical field settings, especially in *sub-humid Mediterranean environments*. *Previous research* generally deals with varietal performance or water management independently, and *it is also not yet clear how the current drought-tolerant varieties will perform* if grown under different water regimes at different growth stages. In the case of northern Tunisia, which faces specific challenges in terms of climate variability and soil limitation, the number of field investigations performed is even lower. Recent Mediterranean research further underscores the value of deficit irrigation strategies in durum wheat systems.

In Morocco, Bourass et al. [10] demonstrated that applying 67% of crop evapotranspiration (ET_c) maintained competitive yields while substantially increasing water productivity under semi-arid conditions. Similarly, studies in Spain by García-Tejero and Durán-Zuazo [11] showed that early-season deficit irrigation can preserve grain yield when appropriately synchronized with crop phenology. In Algeria, Fertas et al. [12] reported significant genotype × irrigation interactions, emphasizing the importance of varietal selection under water-limited environments. In Southern Italy, Montemurro et al. [13] found that coupling regulated deficit irrigation with optimal nitrogen rates supported stable yields and improved efficiency. These region-specific findings confirm that varietal performance under deficit irrigation is highly context-dependent and highlight the need for local field-based evaluations. Our study builds on this body of research by testing two contrasting durum wheat genotypes under three irrigation regimes in a sub-humid Mediterranean environment. Hence, a better understanding of how genotype and irrigation interact to impact essential yield traits, including biomass accumulation, grain yield, and harvest index, would be critical to guide focused adaptation options.

This study aims to evaluate how varietal traits and irrigation levels jointly influence the yield performance and partitioning efficiency of durum wheat in the *sub-humid conditions* of northern Tunisia. Using a factorial field experiment, we compared a traditional variety

(‘Karim’) and an improved cultivar (‘Maali’) across three irrigation treatments (full, half, and rainfed). Our goal is to identify genotype–irrigation combinations that maximize yield potential and improve system resilience under current and projected climate variability, with broader implications for cereal sustainability in Mediterranean agroecosystems.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Site

The experiment was conducted at the Oued Béja Agricultural Experimental Unit, affiliated with the Regional Center for Field Crops Research (CRRGC), situated in northwest Tunisia (36°44′05″N, 9°13′35″E, 165 m a.s.l.). The station spans 350 ha, with 230 ha allocated to cereal cultivation. The area is characterized by a clay-loam soil texture, known for its balanced structure and good retention capacity (Brady & Weil, 2002). The bioclimatic classification of the region is sub-humid Mediterranean, with an annual average rainfall of 510 mm. Climatic data, including minimum and maximum temperatures, rainfall, and relative humidity, were recorded using an automated weather station installed on-site. During the 2021/2022 cropping season, temperatures ranged from 3.5°C to 34.5°C. The selected site reflects typical sub-humid climate conditions representative of northern Tunisia.

Plant Material and Experimental Design Two durum wheat (*Triticum durum* Desf.) varieties were used: ‘Karim’, a traditional cultivar widely grown in Tunisia, and ‘Maali’, a recently released high-yielding variety. ‘Karim’ is characterized by strong tillering and adaptability to dry conditions, but is moderately susceptible to foliar diseases such as rusts and septoria. ‘Maali’, on the other hand, exhibits early maturity, larger grain size, and better resistance to common cereal pathogens, making it a promising candidate under changing climatic conditions.

The experimental design was a randomized complete block design (RCBD) with three replications per treatment. Each elementary plot consisted of six rows, 5 meters long, spaced 36 cm apart, with 1.5-meter alleys between blocks to avoid edge effects. Sowing was performed manually on November 17, 2021, at a seeding rate of 350 viable seeds per square meter, following ICARDA guidelines for durum wheat [14]. All plots received uniform fertilization, weed control, and pest management to ensure that observed effects were primarily due to varietal and irrigation differences.

Irrigation Treatments

Three irrigation treatments were applied: full irrigation (I), half irrigation ($\frac{1}{2}$ I), and rainfed control (P). All treatments were implemented using a pressurized sprinkler system with four sprinklers spaced at 12-meter intervals to guarantee homogeneous water application. The irrigation schedule was synchronized with key crop development stages, and four events were performed on May 16, 20, 23, and 27, 2022. Full irrigation plots received 170 m³/ha per event (total 680 m³/ha), while half irrigation plots received 85 m³/ha per event (total 340 m³/ha); rainfed plots depended solely on natural precipitation. The system was monitored for pressure and flow rate, and no waterlogging or runoff was observed during applications. The use of deficit irrigation simulated realistic field conditions in sub-humid regions, allowing assessment of genotypic performance under water-limited scenarios [15]. Irrigation volumes were selected based on prior regional agronomic data and aligned with recommended wheat water requirements for similar climates.

Soil Sampling and Physicochemical Analysis

Before planting, soil samples were collected from each plot at depths of 20, 40, and 60 cm using a manual auger. Three subsamples per depth were combined into a composite per plot,

placed in clean polyethylene bags, labeled, and transported to the laboratory for analysis. Soil moisture content was determined gravimetrically by weighing fresh soil, oven-drying at 105°C for 24 hours, and reweighing to calculate water loss, following NT 50.21 (1989) procedures. Soil pH was measured using a 1:2.5 soil–water suspension, stirred with a magnetic agitator for 60 minutes, and read using a calibrated pH meter according to ISO 10390 (2005). Electrical conductivity (EC) was measured from a 1:5 soil–water suspension after 60 minutes of decantation using a digital conductivity meter [16]. These parameters provided essential background on soil fertility and salinity, both of which can affect water uptake and nutrient absorption, especially under variable irrigation. Soil data ensured that observed treatment effects were not confounded by major edaphic differences among blocks.

Measurement of Yield Components

At crop maturity, yield components were determined from a central 1 m² area of each plot to avoid border effects. The number of spikes was counted manually from all fertile culms within the demarcated square. Above-ground biomass was then harvested manually, dried in a forced-air oven at 60°C until constant weight, and weighed to obtain biological yield. After threshing the dried material, grains were cleaned and weighed to calculate grain yield, which was extrapolated to kilograms per hectare. A random sample of 1,000 grains from each replicate was counted and weighed using a precision balance to determine thousand kernel weight (TKW). The harvest index (HI) was calculated as grain yield divided by biological yield and expressed as a percentage [7]. All measurements were replicated across blocks and corrected for standard grain moisture (~12%) to maintain consistency. These indicators allowed comparison of genotypic responses under variable water availability and assessment of assimilate partitioning efficiency. Water productivity (WP), also referred to as irrigation water use efficiency, was calculated by dividing the grain yield by the total volume of irrigation water applied for each treatment. Grain yields were measured per plot, extrapolated to a hectare basis, and matched with the known irrigation volumes applied under full (680 m³/ha) and half irrigation (340 m³/ha) regimes. Rainfed treatments were excluded from this calculation. The resulting WP values were used to compare the efficiency of water use across irrigation treatments.

Statistical Analysis

All quantitative data were analyzed using two-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) to assess the effects of wheat variety, irrigation regime, and their interaction on measured variables. Assumptions of normality and homogeneity of variances were verified using the Shapiro-Wilk and Levene's tests, respectively. Where necessary, data were transformed (logarithmic or square-root) to meet statistical assumptions. Post-hoc comparisons were conducted using Tukey's Honest Significant Difference (HSD) test at a significance level of $p < 0.05$. Analyses were performed using SPSS Statistics software, version 20.0. The factorial structure of the design enabled detailed examination of main and interaction effects, improving statistical power and interpretability. Standard error bars and coefficients of variation were calculated for all traits, and no significant outliers were identified. This statistical framework ensured robust conclusions regarding the influence of genotype and water availability on durum wheat performance [7].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Climatic Characterization of the Study Area

To characterize the climate of the study zone, an ombrothermic diagram was elaborated based on 34 years of meteorological data (1986–2018) and presented in Fig. 1(A). In this

diagram, precipitation values were plotted at twice the double scale of temperature to depict dry periods, which are identified at the intersection points of temperature and precipitation curves. Precipitation is predominantly concentrated during the autumn and winter seasons, particularly in December and January, with a monthly average of around 70 mm. In contrast, the dry season spans from May through September, reflecting the region's marked seasonality. Additionally, the 2019–2020 season reveals short-term anomalies. As presented in Fig. 1(B), the monthly evolution of precipitation and temperature at the Oued Béja station highlights an unusual two-month dry spell from early January to early February, which deviates substantially from the dry season observed during the historical data set.

Fig. 1. Monthly variation of precipitation (P) and average temperature (T) at Oued Béja: (A) Long-term climatic profile (1986–2018) highlighting the typical dry season; (B) Seasonal anomaly during the 2021–2022 crop year indicating a two-month dry spell.

This climatic irregularity, corresponding to the 2021–2022 season, could critically affect agronomic processes such as tillering, ultimately reducing spike density and final yield. The above-discussed anomaly coincided with a critical phenological window for wheat development, namely the tillering and early stem elongation stages. These stages are highly sensitive to water availability, as they determine the initiation and survival of tillers, which ultimately influence the number of fertile spikes per unit area. The water deficit during this phase likely limited tiller production, leading to a reduction in spike density and final yield, particularly under rainfed conditions. A phenological timeline overlay (Fig. 2) has been added to better illustrate this alignment between climate stress and crop development.

Understanding both long-term climatic averages and interannual variability is crucial for anticipating stress periods and adopting mitigation procedures. Furthermore, considering the importance of the autumn rainfall period, efforts to synchronize planting schedules with projected rainfall could mitigate yield loss. These observations are particularly relevant for rainfed systems where agriculture is highly dependent on seasonal rains. The pronounced dry season, coupled with increasing variability in rainfall patterns, raises concern about the reliability of traditional rainfed practices. The results also indicate the necessity for further analysis of climate-resilient practices tailored to localized microclimatic profiles, especially in vulnerable areas like Oued Béja. The study by Schilling et al. [3] provides critical insight into how climate change is intensifying extreme events across North Africa, with pronounced consequences for already vulnerable socio-economic and agricultural systems. Their findings indicate that rising temperatures and decreasing precipitation are not only altering average climatic conditions but also increasing the frequency and severity of droughts—particularly in the northwestern parts of the region [3]. In regions like Morocco and Tunisia, where agriculture remains a pillar of food security and livelihoods, extreme climate events translate directly into economic shocks and resource stress [6]. The study reinforces the urgency of reorienting agricultural policies toward adaptation and resilience-building, emphasizing not just the mitigation of average trends but also the preparedness for irregular, high-impact events that challenge the reliability of traditional cropping systems.

Fig. 2. Phenological timeline of wheat development stages over the cropping season, with the January–February dry spell highlighted in red. The dry period coincides with the sensitive tillering and stem elongation stages, which are critical for determining spike density and final yield, particularly under rainfed conditions.

Soil Physico-Chemical Properties

The evaluation of soil pH and electrical conductivity provides insight into the edaphic environment's suitability for durum wheat cultivation. Measurements were performed using a soil-water suspension and direct-reading pH meter. Across all plots, the pH values were consistent and fell within a neutral range, averaging 7.53 ± 0.25 (Table 1). This neutrality indicates favorable conditions for nutrient availability and root development. Furthermore, electrical conductivity values averaged $324 \pm 26.22 \mu\text{s}/\text{cm}$ across the blocks (Table 1), remaining well below the $500 \mu\text{s}/\text{cm}$ threshold that signals salinity concerns. These values suggest that salinity is not a limiting factor in the experimental plots and that soil conditions are unlikely to interfere with water uptake or metabolic processes critical to wheat development. The neutral pH also implies optimal microbial activity and enzyme function in

the soil, both essential for nitrogen fixation and organic matter breakdown. This balance plays a significant role in ensuring steady nutrient cycling during the growing season. Furthermore, stable conductivity values across experimental blocks indicate homogeneous field conditions, enhancing the reliability of treatment comparisons. A low EC is especially important under water-deficit conditions, as high salinity levels can exacerbate water stress by reducing osmotic potential. The implication is that soil properties in the region provide a stable physical baseline, allowing researchers to isolate the effects of irrigation regimes and varietal differences more confidently. This observation supports the conclusion that observed yield variations stem primarily from experimental variables rather than soil inconsistencies. Overall, the edaphic context underpins the broader physiological responses documented in the subsequent sections and validates the experimental integrity. The availability of nutrients is not solely dictated by their sorption dynamics in soil, but also by how pH influences root uptake processes, often in divergent ways [17]. Soil salinity may affect crop growth and yield by disrupting key physiological processes and root growth, particularly through ionic toxicity and osmotic imbalance [18].

Table 1: Soil pH and Electrical Conductivity (EC) in Experimental Blocks at Oued Béja During the 2021/2022 Cropping Season

Block	pH	EC ($\mu\text{s/cm}$)
R1	7.79	300
R2	7.54	320
R3	7.27	352
Mean \pm SD	7.53 \pm 0.25	324 \pm 26.22

Note: Mean values and standard deviations (\pm SD) of soil pH and EC ($\mu\text{s/cm}$) measured at 0–60 cm depth across three blocks. The pH was measured in a 1:2.5 soil–water suspension using a calibrated pH meter, and EC was determined in a 1:5 soil–water suspension using a conductivity meter.

Effect of Irrigation Regime

Irrigation regime significantly affected multiple yield components (Fig. 3). Among these, spike density was most sensitive, with deficit irrigation resulting in the highest average (307.83 ± 20.78 spikes/m²), followed by full irrigation (251.83 ± 53.71) and rainfed conditions (225.50 ± 27.03). These findings highlight that water stress management during early crop development stages plays a crucial role in determining reproductive success. This is consistent with Farooq et al. (2009), who reported improved reproductive traits under moderate drought due to enhanced resource allocation. Similarly, Blum [19] emphasized that yield stability under limited water depends largely on effective stress timing and crop adaptability.

Fig. 3. Effect of water regime on spike number per square meter (SN) in durum wheat. Treatments include full irrigation (D), half irrigation (I), and rainfed (P) conditions. Bars represent mean values \pm standard deviation. Different letters above bars indicate significant differences among treatments according to Tukey's HSD test ($p < 0.05$).

Biological yield followed a similar pattern, peaking under deficit irrigation (1083.33 ± 255.55 g/m²), compared to rainfed (956.67 ± 143.65 g/m²) and full irrigation (797.50 ± 76.27 g/m²) (Fig. 4 (A)). These differences were statistically significant, underlining the positive response of biomass accumulation to well-managed stress. Interestingly, grain yield—though highest under deficit irrigation (499.44 ± 42.20)—did not show statistically significant variation across treatments, indicating that moderate stress might not negatively affect final grain output (Fig. 4 (B)). Zhang et al. [20] also demonstrated that moderate water limitation can enhance biomass accumulation by promoting photosynthetic efficiency and better assimilate allocation. In line with this, Geerts and Raes [21] emphasized that deficit irrigation can preserve yield levels while improving water-use efficiency, reinforcing its value in sustainable agriculture.

This aligns with prior studies suggesting that reduced irrigation can trigger compensatory mechanisms like increased assimilate partitioning to grains. Thousand grain weight (TKW) and harvest index (HI) presented nuanced trends. Rainfed conditions yielded the highest TKW (47.28 ± 1.48 g), possibly due to lower biomass competition. In contrast, HI was highest under full irrigation (0.555 ± 0.056 g) (Fig. 5), reflecting efficient biomass conversion under optimal moisture. These results suggest that while deficit irrigation enhances certain morphological traits, full irrigation supports more balanced physiological efficiency. The results collectively support precision irrigation strategies for resource optimization in sub-humidagroecosystems. Similar findings were reported by Luquet et al. [22], who observed that grain traits like TKW responded positively to mild water stress due to reduced inter-plant competition. Additionally, Sadras and Lawson [23] emphasized that harvest index benefits from optimal irrigation, as improved water status enhances assimilate transport and reproductive allocation. These findings reinforce the importance of tailoring irrigation to crop stage and trait sensitivity.

Fig. 4. Effect of water regime on (A) biological yield (BY, g/m²) and (B) grain yield (GY, g/m²) in durum wheat. Water regimes include full irrigation (D), half irrigation (I), and rainfed conditions (P). Bars represent mean values \pm standard deviation. Different letters above the bars indicate statistically significant differences between treatments according to Tukey's HSD test ($p < 0.05$).

Water productivity (WP), defined as the grain yield per unit of irrigation water applied, differed significantly between irrigation treatments. As shown in Table 2, WP deficit irrigation (1.29 kg/m³) was substantially higher than that under full irrigation (0.73 kg/m³). This difference was statistically significant ($p < 0.05$), as indicated by the assigned group letters. The higher WP observed under deficit irrigation confirms the greater efficiency of this regime in converting limited water inputs into grain yield. This outcome aligns with previous studies (e.g., [21]; [24]), which highlight the potential of deficit to maintain or even enhance yield performance while significantly reducing water consumption. Under full irrigation, although total yield was marginally higher, the amount of water used was disproportionate, leading to a lower return per unit of water applied.

These findings strongly support the strategic use of moderate deficit irrigation in water-scarce environments like northern Tunisia. By achieving nearly double the WP compared to full irrigation, this regime ensures a more sustainable and resource-efficient production system. The results reinforce the broader argument that irrigation strategies should prioritize efficiency over maximization, particularly in the face of increasing climate variability and declining freshwater availability.

Fig. 5. Effect of water regime on harvest index (HI) in durum wheat.

Water treatments include full irrigation (D), half irrigation (I), and rainfed conditions (P). Bars represent mean values \pm standard deviation. Different letters above the bars indicate statistically significant differences among treatments according to Tukey's HSD test ($p < 0.05$).

Table 2. Water Productivity under different irrigation regimes

Treatment	Water Productivity (kg/m ³)	Standard Error (SE)	Group
Full Irrigation	0.73	0.10	b
Deficit Irrigation	1.29	0.20	a

Note: Different letters indicate significant differences at $p < 0.05$ (Tukey's HSD)

Effect of Variety

Varietal responses further influenced yield performance. The older variety Karim demonstrated higher biological yield (956.00 ± 189.14) g/m², indicating better vegetative growth (Fig.6 (A)). However, the ameliorated variety Maali presented greater spike density in m² (284 ± 23.56) (Fig.6 (B)) and grain yield (484.74 ± 45.43) g/m², suggesting improved reproductive efficiency (Fig.6 (C) and Fig.6 (D)). Although grain yield differences were not statistically significant, Maali showed a higher TKW (41.91 ± 3.36) and HI (0.585 ± 0.049), affirming its suitability for environments with fluctuating water availability (Fig.6 (E)). These outcomes are consistent with previous research indicating that newer varieties bred under stress conditions tend to allocate more resources to grain production rather than vegetative structures. Maali's high spike density implies better tillering capacity, possibly due to genetic improvements in early vigor and root architecture. Its improved HI emphasizes its ability to optimize biomass partitioning, making it more desirable for future climate scenarios. In contrast, Karim's performance in biological yield suggests its potential role in forage-oriented systems or in high-input environments where water and nutrients are not limiting. Together, these findings affirm the necessity of matching varietal selection to environmental conditions and production goals. The comparative analysis supports breeding efforts aimed at combining high TGW with efficient resource use. In sum, both irrigation regime and varietal choice independently and interactively shape yield outcomes in durum wheat systems. Such observations align with Zhang et al. [25], who noted that modern wheat cultivars show increased reproductive allocation under water-limited conditions, enhancing yield stability. Similarly, Reynolds et al. [26] emphasized that targeted breeding for traits like early vigor, root efficiency, and partitioning capacity is key to developing genotypes suited to future climate variability.

Fig. 6. Effect of variety on key yield-related traits in durum wheat.

Comparison between the older cultivar Karim and the improved cultivar Maali for (A) biological yield (BY, g/m²), (B) spike number per square meter (SN, spikes/m²), (C) grain yield (GY, g/m²), (D) thousand kernel weight (TKW, g), and (E) harvest index (HI). Bars represent mean values \pm standard deviation. Different letters above bars indicate significant differences between varieties according to Tukey's HSD test ($p < 0.05$).

Effect of Variety, Irrigation Regime, and Their Interaction on Yield Components

The statistical analysis demonstrated that variety, irrigation regime, and their interaction had significant effects on biological yield, grain yield, and harvest index (IR) (Table 3). For biological yield, both variety ($F = 28.35$, $p < 0.001$) and irrigation regime ($F = 14.31$, $p = 0.001$) were highly significant, along with their interaction ($F = 6.50$, $p = 0.012$), suggesting that biomass accumulation was influenced by both genotype and water availability. Grain yield showed even stronger interaction effects ($F = 51.87$, $p < 0.001$), indicating a pronounced genotype-by-environment response. For IR, the most substantial effect was variety ($F = 48.37$, $p < 0.001$), followed by interaction ($F = 13.43$, $p = 0.001$) and irrigation ($F = 4.80$, $p = 0.029$), highlighting how partitioning efficiency is shaped by both genetic background and water supply. In the interaction table, Karim, the older variety, achieved the highest biological yield under full irrigation (1300.0 g/m²), while Maali, the improved cultivar, reached only 866.7 g/m² under the same condition. However, under reduced irrigation and rainfed conditions, Maali showed much greater stability in biomass production. When shifting from full to half irrigation, Karim's biomass dropped by nearly 37%, whereas Maali's decrease was only about 11%. This

suggests that Karim depends heavily on high water input, typical of older varieties bred under irrigated conditions without selection pressure for drought resilience. In contrast, Maali's more stable biomass production reflects improved stress adaptability, a common trait in modern genotypes selected under sub-humid conditions. More strikingly, in terms of grain yield, Maali outperformed all other combinations under rainfed conditions with 551.7 g/m², while Karim yielded only 373.5 g/m². This pattern reversed under full irrigation, where Karim had a slightly higher yield (535.7 g/m²) compared to Maali (463.2 g/m²). The severe decline in Karim's grain yield under stress emphasizes its vulnerability, while Maali's strong performance in rainfed and moderate irrigation treatments underscores its genetic improvements for drought resilience and reproductive stability. Such performance is consistent with breeding objectives for modern wheat cultivars, which prioritize yield stability and water-use efficiency rather than peak performance under ideal conditions [24]. The harvest index (IR) further confirms this physiological advantage. Maali consistently demonstrated higher IR across all treatments, with the highest under rainfed conditions (0.651) and the lowest observed in Karim under the same conditions (0.354). High IR under stress indicates efficient biomass partitioning to grain, a trait intentionally selected in modern wheat breeding programs to ensure productivity under water-limited environments [26]. Even when both varieties received full irrigation, Maali still showed a superior IR (0.535) compared to Karim (0.415), suggesting that the improved genotype maintains a more favorable source-sink balance across environments.

Table 3. Statistical significance of the effects of variety, irrigation regime, and their interaction on biological yield, grain yield, and harvest index (IR) in durum wheat.

Trait	Factor	F-value	p-value	Significance
Biological Yield	Variety	28.35	< 0.001	Highly significant
	Irrigation Regime	14.31	0.001	Highly significant
	Variety × Irrigation	6.50	0.012	Significant interaction
Grain Yield	Variety	(not shown)		Strong effects inferred
	Irrigation Regime	(not shown)		
	Variety × Irrigation	51.87	< 0.001	Very highly significant
Harvest Index (IR)	Variety	48.37	< 0.001	Strongest individual effect
	Irrigation Regime	4.80	0.029	Moderately significant
	Variety × Irrigation	13.43	0.001	Significant interaction

To further explore the significant variety × irrigation interaction observed in the ANOVA ($F = 51.87$, $p < 0.001$), an interaction plot was generated to visualize grain yield responses of the two wheat genotypes across irrigation regimes (Fig. 7). The plot reveals a clear crossover interaction, confirming that the varieties responded differently to water availability. Karim achieved its maximum grain yield under deficit irrigation (D) but experienced a marked decline under rainfed conditions (P). This pattern suggests that Karim benefits from moderate water stress, potentially due to more favorable biomass partitioning or transient physiological adaptations under limited water supply. However, its performance was not sustained under severe water deficit, indicating limited drought resilience. In contrast, Maali exhibited an inverse trend. Yield was lowest under full irrigation (I) and progressively improved under deficit (D) and rainfed (P) conditions, with peak performance under rainfed treatment. This response highlights Maali's strong adaptability to low-input or drought-prone environments, likely supported by intrinsic drought-tolerance mechanisms such as deeper rooting, efficient stomatal control, or stay-green traits previously reported in similar genotypes. These results underline the importance of matching genotype to water management strategy. While Karim may be suitable for systems employing regulated deficit irrigation, Maali emerges as a superior option for rainfed agriculture, particularly in semi-arid environments. The crossover nature of

the interaction provides strong empirical support for the inclusion of interaction analysis in varietal selection under contrasting irrigation scenarios.

Fig. 6. Interaction plot of grain yield (GY) for two wheat varieties (Karim and Maali) under three irrigation regimes: full irrigation (I), deficit irrigation (D), and rainfed (P). Error bars represent standard errors. The crossover interaction illustrates differential varietal responses to water availability, with Maali performing best under rainfed conditions and Karim under deficit irrigation

CONCLUSION

This study provides evidence that varietal selection and irrigation management jointly influence yield outcomes in durum wheat systems under Mediterranean sub-humid conditions. The improved variety ‘Maali’ demonstrated robust physiological and reproductive performance across all irrigation regimes, particularly excelling under deficit and rainfed treatments. Its superior spike density, grain yield stability, and elevated harvest index highlight its adaptability to water-limited environments—traits aligned with the goals of modern wheat breeding. In contrast, the traditional variety ‘Karim’ showed high biomass productivity only under full irrigation but underperformed in stress scenarios, suggesting its utility is restricted to high-input or forage-oriented systems. Deficit irrigation, surprisingly, emerged as the most efficient treatment for several traits, including biological yield and spike number, without significantly compromising grain yield. This supports deficit irrigation as a viable strategy to conserve water while maintaining productivity in semi-arid and sub-humid regions. Soil homogeneity and favorable physicochemical properties further validate that observed yield differences were primarily due to varietal and irrigation effects rather than edaphic variability. Overall, the study underscores the necessity of tailoring genotype selection and water management strategies to local environmental conditions. In the face of projected climate change impacts, integrating stress-resilient cultivars like ‘Maali’ with optimized irrigation

regimes offers a sustainable path toward food security and cereal system resilience in Tunisia and comparable agroecosystems. These findings offer valuable guidance for policymakers, breeders, and agronomists aiming to future-proof wheat production against increasing climatic variability. Future research should integrate physiological measurements to better understand the mechanisms underlying genotype performance under water-limited conditions, particularly traits such as rooting depth and stomatal regulation.

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